

4sU-seq protocol (Lammer et al. 2022)

4-thiouridine (4sU) labeling and RNA isolation

Nascent RNA labeling was performed using a protocol adapted by the Goodrich-Kugel Lab (CU-Boulder) from Garibaldi et al., 2017 (doi: 10.1007/978-1-4939-7204-3_13). Each cell line was grown to about 80% confluence (about 7 million cells) on 10 cm dishes in stripped-serum DMEM over 48 hours. Cell culture conditions were as stated above. Media was replaced with stripped-serum DMEM containing 100 nM dexamethasone for the treated samples or 0.01% ethanol (volume equivalent) for untreated samples. During the final hour of each treatment, media was supplemented with 200 μ M 4-thiouridine (4sU, MilliporeSigma) to label newly transcribed RNAs. Specifically, half of the media was removed, 4sU was mixed in, and the media was transferred back to the dish. The untreated sample received 4sU for 1 hour as well. At the end of treatment, media was aspirated and cells were lysed by adding 3 mL TRIzol (Invitrogen) directly to the dish and incubating for 5 minutes. Cell lysate was then transferred to 15 mL conical tubes and frozen at -70 °C for long-term storage. To extract total RNA from the cell lysate, the 3 mL of lysate was split into 1 mL aliquots in Phase Lock Gel tubes (5PRIME, Heavy). Then, 200 μ L chloroform was added to each tube and tubes were shaken vigorously by hand for 15 seconds. Tubes were centrifuged at 12,000 x g for 15 minutes at 4 °C and the separated aqueous layer on top of the three tubes was combined in a 15 mL conical tube. To precipitate the RNA, 1.5 mL isopropanol was added to the 15 mL conical and incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes. The sample was again split into 3 smaller aliquots and centrifuged at 12,000 x g for 10 minutes at 4 °C to pellet. Supernatant was carefully discarded and 1 mL of 75% ethanol was added to each tube to wash pellets. Tubes were centrifuged at 7,500 x g for 5 minutes at 4 °C and ethanol was discarded, taking care to remove any residual ethanol. Pellets were resuspended in 15 μ L nuclease-free water and combined. Isolated RNA was quantified with a NanoDrop spectrometer and diluted to 1 μ g/ μ L. RNA was then stored at -70 °C.

4sU-labeled RNA biotinylation and pulldown

Biotinylation was performed using a protocol adapted by the Goodrich-Kugel Lab (CU-Boulder) from Garibaldi et al., 2017 (doi: 10.1007/978-1-4939-7204-3_13). To biotinylate 4sU-labeled RNAs, we mixed 50-70 μ g of total RNA with the biotinylation reaction buffer containing 10 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 1 mM EDTA, and 0.1 mg/mL biotin-MTSEA-XX in dimethylformamide (Biotium). Reaction was brought to 250 μ L total with nuclease-free water and carried out for 30 minutes in the dark (foil-wrapped) at room temperature with nutation. Following the incubation, the reaction was moved to a Phase Lock Gel tube and mixed with 250 μ L phenol/chloroform pH 6.7. The tube was shaken vigorously by hand for 15 seconds and centrifuged at 12,000 x g for 5 minutes at 4 °C and the separated aqueous layer on top was transferred to a new tube. The RNA was then precipitated by adding 20 μ L 5 M NaCl and 200 μ L isopropanol and inverting to mix. The sample was then spun at 16,000 x g for 20 minutes at 4 °C to pellet and supernatant was discarded. Then, 500 μ L of cold 75% ethanol was added to wash the pellets and the sample was spun at 16,000 x g for 10 minutes at 4 °C. All ethanol was removed and pellets were resuspended in 26 μ L nuclease-free water. Biotinylated RNA was quantified with a NanoDrop spectrometer and diluted to 1 μ g/ μ L. Immediately following quantification, streptavidin pulldown of biotinylated RNAs was performed using the μ MACS streptavidin kit (Miltenyi Biotec). Biotinylated RNA was heated to 65 °C for 10 minutes and left on ice for at least 5 minutes. During heating and cooling, high-salt wash buffer was prepared with 100 mM Tris pH 7.4, 10 mM EDTA, 1 M NaCl, 0.1% Tween 20. After the ice incubation, biotinylated RNA was mixed with 100 μ L of streptavidin beads and incubated at room temperature with nutation for 15

minutes. During incubation, a μ MACS column was pre-equilibrated by twice running 100 μ L of Equilibration Buffer for Nucleic Acid applications from the kit over the column. Bead-bound RNA was then transferred to the column. After the initial flow through finished, beads were washed twice with 500 μ L high-salt wash buffer. Biotinylated RNA was then eluted twice each with 100 μ L freshly-prepared 100 mM DTT and collected in a new tube containing 500 μ L ice-cold 100% ethanol. The tube was then incubated at -20 °C for 30 minutes or overnight to precipitate. The RNA was then pelleted by spinning at 16,000 x g for 30 minutes at 4 °C. The supernatant was then discarded and 500 μ L of ice-cold 75% ethanol was added to wash. The sample was spun at 16,000 x g for 15 minutes at 4 °C and all ethanol was removed. The tube was allowed to air dry open at room temperature for 2 minutes. The RNA pellet was resuspended in 20 μ L nuclease-free water and quantified using the Qubit RNA high sensitivity reagents (Invitrogen, Q32852). Typical yields were 2% of total RNA used for biotinylation. Biotinylation and pulldown were done in sample replicate pairs to reduce variability from the pulldown. The quality and integrity of purified RNA was assessed using a TapeStation (Agilent).

Biotinylated RNA library preparation and sequencing

RNA libraries were prepared using the KAPA RNA HyperPrep kit with RiboErase (Roche). 400 ng of biotinylated RNA was used as input. Dual-index adapters including unique molecular identifiers were used to avoid PCR duplicates (IDT, xGen UDI-UMI adapters). Libraries were PCR amplified for 8 cycles and their quality was assessed by TapeStation. Libraries were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSEQ 6000 for 2x150 bp paired-end reads at the University of Colorado School of Medicine Genomics and Microarray Core Facility. Samples were sequenced to 24-36 million reads.